

EFFECT OF FIBER–POLYMER SOLUBILITY ON INTERFACIAL MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER- REINFORCED BMI COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The growing uses of carbon fiber reinforced composites in many engineering applications has made the issue of interface a major focus of interest in the design and manufacture of composite. In this study, The Flory–Huggins parameter and the solubility parameter of carbon fibers and BMI resins were determined by inverse gas chromatograph (IGC) with the variety of well characterized solvent probes. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of carbon fibers/BMI composites were investigated by micro-droplet test and the correlation of the fiber-matrix solubility parameter with interfacial mechanical properties was discussed. The results indicate that the interface strength increased with the decrease of $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ values for carbon fiber- reinforced BMI composites. The surface diffusion of fiber-matrix was found to have a basic character for the interface compatibility in carbon fiber reinforced composites. The solubility parameter can be applied to predict the physic-chemical interaction of composite interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

Molecular diffusion is an important process in many two-phase interface systems for the devolatilization of small residuals from the polymer bulk. A common method of quantification uses the solubility parameter which represents the square root of the cohesive energy density. Thus it is directly related to the stability and other physical properties of a material. The solubility parameter was originally derived by Scatchard and Hildebrand for regular solutions^[3]. However, its application can be extended to simple solid/liquid or solid/ solid systems. Many studies focused on the diffusion of interface but little investigated relation between the solubility and the interface of carbon fiber-reinforced composites for its difficult to determine the diffusion coefficients for carbon fiber and resin. Inverse gas chromatography (IGC) has been used in measuring diffusion coefficients as a favored method especially for the amorphous or partially amorphous macromolecules^[4,5].

With the variety of well characterized solvent probes, IGC was available for the calculation of the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter and the solubility parameter rapidly and precisely. A single fiber fragmentation test has been used as to investigate IFSS. The solubility parameters of carbon fiber and BMI resin were characterized seriously and the correlation with interfacial mechanical properties was discussed in the work.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 Materials

Two high-strength PAN based carbon fibers T300B-3000-40B(T300) and CF300-3000-1(CF300) with similar tensile strength and modulus corresponding to different manufacturer has been used in this study. Two BMI resin used in this study, BMI 1 was composed of 4,4-bismaleimido-diphenylmethane, O,O-diallylbisphenol A and other additives BMI 2 was 4,4-bismaleimido-diphenylmethane and O,O-diallylbisphenol A with 100:85 weight ratio. The solvents used in IGC were supplied by Sigma–Aldrich. All these adsorbates were HPLC grade or high purity solvents and used as purchased.

2.2 Apparatus and procedure

IGC experiments were carried out at infinite dilution using an SMS-iGC (UK). The neutral probes in these investigations were decane, nonane, octane and heptane, the polar probes included toluene, ethanol and acetone. Data relating to all probes is presented in Table 1. The carbon fiber and BMI resin were packed into the 4 mm internal diameter and 300 mm length of SMS standard passivated glass columns. The amount of the samples was 0.8 g. Methane was used as a non-interacting marker for dead-time measurements. Helium was used as carrier gas, and the flow rate was 10 ml/min. The adsorption experiments were carried out at 30°C. The data calculation was made by the SMS-iGC analysis software (v1.2.5).

Probe	properties	DN	AN*	Surface Tension (J/m ²)	Cross Sectional Area (m ²)
n-Heptane	Neutral	-	-	0.0234	7.5E-19
n-Octane	Neutral	-	-	0.0227	6.9E-19
n-Nonane	Neutral	-	-	0.0213	6.3E-19
n-Decane	Neutral	-	-	0.0203	5.73E-19
Toluene	Base	20.3	14.33	0.0285	4.6E-19
Ethanol	Acid	20.0	10.3	0.0211	3.53E-19
Acetone	Base	17.0	2.5	0.0165	3.4E-19

Table 1 Properties of the probes used in the current work

3 IGC THEORY

Solubility effects can be studied by pulse inverse gas chromatography at infinite dilution. As in analytical gas chromatography, the retention time was as primary information^[6-8]. The retention time can be converted into a retention volume, which is directly related to various physico-chemical properties of the material.

The net retention volume V_R^0 determined by Equation 1

$$V_R^0 = j/m \cdot F \cdot (t_R - t_0) \frac{T}{273.5} \quad (1)$$

where T is the column temperature, m is the sample mass, F is the carrier gas flow rate, t_R is the retention time taken for the probe and t₀ is the time necessary for a nonadsorbing probe (methane) through the column (dead time), j is the James-Martin correction, which depend on the pressure at column inlet and outlet.

The activity coefficient Ω can be obtained from the retention volume

$$\ln \Omega = \ln(273.15 * R / (p^0 * M_1 * V_R^0)) - p^0 * (B_{11} - V_1) / (R * T) \quad (2)$$

where p^0 is the saturation pressure, M the molecular mass, B_{11} the second virial coefficient and V_1 the molecular volume of the probe molecule at column temperature.

The Flory-Huggins-parameter χ can be derived from equation (3)

$$\chi = \ln \Omega + \ln(\rho_1 / \rho_2) - (1 - (V_1 / V_2)) \quad (3)$$

Where ρ is the liquid density and V again the molecular volume.

Now using the approach from DiPaola and Guillet a linear equation can be formed:

$$\frac{\delta_1^2}{RT} - \frac{\chi}{V_1} = \left(\frac{2\delta_2}{RT} \right) * \delta_1 - \left(\frac{2\delta_2^2}{RT} - \frac{\chi_s}{V_1} \right) \quad (4)$$

δ_1 is the solubility parameter of the probe molecule, δ_2 the solubility parameter of the resin, χ the entropic contribution to the Flory-Huggins parameter and V_1 the molar volume of the probe molecule. If the left- hand side versus δ_1 yields, δ_2 can then be determined from the slope.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Solubility parameter

The measured solubility parameters of the samples are based on the decane, nonane, octane, heptane, toluene, ethanol, acetone probes which has different solubility parameters. The retention volume can be converted into an activity coefficient, which is used to calculate the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter. The Flory-Huggins interaction parameter between probes and samples are summarized in table 2.

adsorbate	χ			
	T300	CF300	BMI-1	BMI-2
Decane	6.79	6.88	4.09	3.55
Nonane	6.85	6.94	4.38	3.85
Octane	6.90	7.01	4.71	4.21
Heptane	6.70	6.80	4.73	4.36
Toluene	6.33	5.67	4.74	4.16
Ethanol	6.27	6.35	4.54	4.42
Acetone	5.83	5.60	4.09	4.12

Table 2 Flory-Huggins interaction parameters (χ) between probes and samples

As it can be observed, the values of the Flory–Huggins interaction parameters values increased with the increase of chain length in the n-alkane series. This trend was observed at all four samples. A similar trend has been observed earlier with other polymer solutions^[4]. This can be related to the increase of the free volume of the solvent: the Flory–Huggins parameter is obtained by entropic and enthalpic components. The entropic one, mainly due to the free volume of the solvent, increased with chain length in the n-alkane series. The second one influenced by the interactions between the polymer chains and the solvent.

Figure 1: The solubility parameter for fibers and resins

The solubility parameters of carbons and resins were calculated from Flory-Huggins interaction parameters of a series of probes with the method developed by DiPaola and Guillet and showed in Figure 1. The solubility parameter of the CF300 and T300 fibers were 11.90 MPa^{1/2} and 11.82 MPa^{1/2}, the solubility parameter of the BMI-1 and BMI-2 resins were 11.39 MPa^{1/2} and 11.36 MPa^{1/2}, respectively.

4.2 Interfacial shear strength of carbon fiber/BMI composite

The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of carbon fibers/BMI composites were investigated by micro-droplet test. The matrix resin was wetted onto the single carbon fiber to form a micro-droplet surrounding the diameter of carbon fiber due to the function of surface tension. The micro-droplet resin was cured for 1 h at 150 °C, 4 h at 200 °C. The embedded length of each micro-droplet was measured through optical microscopic observation. The knives came in contact with the solid resin droplet and the force required to debond the droplet from the fiber was recorded. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was calculated from Eq (5).

$$\tau_{IFSS} = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi d \cdot 2r} \quad (5)$$

Where τ_{IFSS} is interfacial shear strength, F_{max} is the maximum load, d is the fiber diameter and $2r$ is the embedded length. The experiment should be repeated at least 20 times for each kind of samples. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the IFSS of CF300/BMI-1 and CF300/BMI-2 were 117.8MPa and 95.5MPa, the IFSS of T300/BMI-1 and T300/BMI-2 were 80.4MPa and 68.8MPa, respectively.

Figure 2: Change of IFSS with the solubility parameters of carbons and resins

The variation of carbon fiber–BMI composite IFSS with the solubility parameters is shown in Fig. 2. The $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ value was used to indicate the similarity of solubility parameters between fiber and resin in this work. As it can be observed, the IFSS value for CF300/BMI-1 is clearly higher than for CF300/BMI-2 while the $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ value of CF300/BMI-1 is clearly smaller than that of CF300/BMI-2. This trend was observed at all other samples: T300/BMI-1 and T300/BMI-2, CF300/BMI-1 and T300/BMI-1, CF300/BMI-2 and T300/BMI-2, the IFSS values linearly increased with the $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ values decreased. This can be related to the similarity of solubility parameters: the much smaller of the $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ values, the higher of the interfacial strength of the composite, which implies a better bonding at the fiber-matrix interface. The interface in composite has a substantial thickness, which may be formed by the interdiffusion of atoms or molecules across the interface, and its chemical, physical and mechanical properties are different from those of either the fiber or the matrix. Interdiffusion depends on the amount of diffusion, the amount of molecular entanglement and the strength of the bonding between the molecules. As Hansen introduced, the solubility parameter is a numerical value that indicates the relative solvency behavior, which is related to the strength of the dispersive, polar and hydrogen bonding interactions. Therefore, the resin and fiber diffusion plays an important role in promoting physical adsorption, chemical bonding, electrostatic attraction and other reactions between elements of each constituent at the interface region. Solubility parameters was proven useful for the prediction of the interface compatibility in carbon fiber reinforced BMI composites.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The Flory–Huggins parameter and the solubility parameter have been obtained for carbon fibers and BMI resins by means of IGC measurements. A single fiber fragmentation test has been used as to investigate the IFSS of carbon fibers reinforced BMI composites. The obtained values of the composition indicate the IFSS values is a variable which has a good influence over the solubility parameter (the lower the $|\delta_f - \delta_r|$ values, the higher the interface strength). The surface diffusion of fiber-matrix was found to have a basic character for the interface compatibility in carbon fiber reinforced BMI composites. The solubility parameter can be applied to predict the physico-chemical interaction of composite interface.

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